

INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD.

Muradov Sirojiddin Husan oqli

Intern-teacher of the Department of
"Labor Protection and Technical Safety"
of the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics
Karshi, Uzbekistan

sirojiddinmuradov0@gmail.com

orcid.org/0009-0001-4270-8600

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Abstract. In this article, the personal opinions of the authors about the comfort and safe working conditions for workers in the field of labor protection by organizing work with the help of the "Kaizen" method are presented. The article is intended for the requirements of labor protection and technical safety directions, labor protection and safety specialists, and general readers.

Key words: "Kaizen", occupational diseases, damage, 5s, ergonomics, work activity, harmful and dangerous factor.

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЙ ТРУДА И ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ С ПОМОЩЬЮ МЕТОДА КАЙДЗЕН.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены личные мнения авторов о комфортных и безопасных условиях труда работников сферы охраны труда при организации труда с помощью метода «Кайдзен». Статья предназначена для требований направлений охраны труда и технической безопасности, специалистов по охране труда и технике безопасности, а также широкого круга читателей.

Ключевые слова: «Кайдзен», профессиональные заболевания, вред, 5с, эргономика, трудовая деятельность, вредный и опасный фактор.

INTRODUCTION.

The word "kaizen" comes from the Japanese language and translates as "writing in more detail". This method can be used not only in the field of business, but also in various fields. With the help of this manual, it is possible to make small or large changes in various fields, that is, to learn, improve and increase the level of success. This method does not require a lot of time and money, but in the long run it is very effective in improving the quality of work. Enables the application of the Kaizen method to safe working conditions. With this approach, there is a greater focus on safety and health in the workplace, as well as a focus on improving safety and improving quality by making small or large changes every day. As a result, employees will be more motivated and able to perform better while making positive changes in the workplace. Also, the "Kaizen" method helps to increase external and internal security, automate operations and reduce large costs[1].

RESEARCH METHODS.

Methods such as analysis of scientific and educational literature, comparative analysis, generalization, programming and digitization models were used in the research process.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS OBTAINED.

The method called "Kaizen" is taken from the Japanese language, which translates as "writing in more detail". This method is used not only in the field of business, but also in various fields [1] [2].

With this method, it is possible to make small or large changes every day, that is, to learn more detailed possibilities, improve work performance and increase the level of success. This method does not require a lot of time and money, and is very effective in improving the quality of work in the long run. When promoting this method to the field of labor protection, we must first learn what labor protection is. Labor protection is socio-economic, organizational, technical, sanitary-hygiene and treatment-prophylactic measures aimed at ensuring the safety, health and working ability of a person in the labor process, acting on the basis of the relevant law and other regulatory documents, and consists of a system of tools [4] [5].

"Kaizen" method helps to increase external and internal security, automate operations and reduce significant costs. The formation of this method was mainly carried out in Japanese outsourcing companies, and it helped to improve the quality of their effective workplace. And today, this style is helping the success of high-quality workplaces. For example: Providing work activities related to sitting work to employees who have problems with walking. And in addition to this, all the necessary tools and raw materials should be placed in such a way and technology that the employee does not feel that he has a problem with walking and does not affect the continuation of work.

The "Kaizen" method is based on several examples, which are:

- Making changes to reduce the distance of one car and increase its safety;
- Improving the workplace through the exchange of workers;
- Communicating with workers and taking their suggestions into account, and improving operations by implementing suggestions;
- Sending workers to study in order to improve work activities;
- Providing high-quality service to customers by improving quality and changing the methods of implementation in all services;
- To review and change work activities in order to improve external and internal security;
- To reduce high costs in the workplace, review these costs and reduce costs according to requirements;
- With the help of changing mastery in all activities, mastery of work and creation of comfort in the workplace, thereby eliminating factors that lead to occupational diseases;
- Increasing the volume of work and warning of danger through effective use of modern information devices [6,10];
- Ensuring the transfer of safety instructions based on digital technologies [7,9].

Through these directions, the "Kaizen" method helps to achieve success, and this method is very effective in order to use continuous improvement, provide high quality service, ensure safe and comfortable working conditions and increase safety in the workplace.

CONCLUSION.

The following goals can be achieved in the field of labor protection through the "Kaizen" method:

1. Safety: The Kaizen method helps ensure the safety of workers by increasing safety and implementing high-quality work with mandatory safety requirements.

2. Improving quality: This method not only helps to ensure the safety of workers, but also helps to improve the quality of service. Using the "Kaizen" method, it is possible to achieve efficient use of the labor of disabled employees.

3. Cost reduction: "Kaizen" method helps to reduce costs by optimizing work activities. In order to reduce costs through this method, it is possible to achieve success by creating a comfortable environment for employees, reviewing production costs and reducing costs accordingly.

It is possible to effectively implement labor protection works using the "Kaizen" method in production. Improving the quality of the workplace can be achieved by providing employees with high-quality working conditions. Improving the quality of the workplace can be improved through the "Kaizen" method. This method helps not only to ensure the safety of workers, but also to improve the quality of work.

The quality of the workplace and working conditions can be improved through the following methods:

1. Skills and knowledge of workers: Training, seminars, and other external training should be organized to improve the skills of workers [11,12,13].

2. Start every day with the principles of "5S" (labor rationalization system in production): "5S" principles, namely Seiri (sorting), Seiton (placing), Seiso (cleaning), Seiketsu (ordering) and Shitsuke (release) are principles that help to improve quality every day at the workplace [3,7,8].

3. Improve communication between workers: Communication helps to reduce mistakes between workers while doing things successfully in the workplace. In order to improve the communication process, it is necessary to increase the relations between the workers, follow their understanding and explain the important deadlines correctly.

4. Making changes every day: Every day, small or big changes should be made in the workplace. With the help of changes, it is possible to optimize the service process and increase the quality.

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